

Integrative cross-scale label-free optical imaging of bioelectrical phenomena

Sidahmed Abayzeed,

Optics and Photonics Research Group, Faculty of Engineering, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, UK

sidahmed.abayzeed2@nottingham.ac.uk

Abstract – Bioelectricity is increasingly recognized as a fundamental principle in biology, with pioneering research demonstrating its roles in wound healing, morphogenesis, and cancer metastasis. Compelling research extends its scope beyond neurons and cardiac cells to include cells that are traditionally classified as non-excitable. Bioelectric phenomena operate across multiple scales, from the molecular level to entire organisms, and across timescales spanning microseconds to a full lifespan. However, current measurement approaches only sparsely sample this broad spatial and temporal continuum, and they are not built for cross-scale integration. This Perspective proposes a conceptual framework for investigating bioelectrical functions across scales. It presents a spatial and temporal measurement workspace that hosts a diverse array of trajectories, each tied to specific hypotheses and cross-scale measurement strategies. Key examples of its advantages include exploring emergent spatiotemporal patterns, for instance, by imaging ion channel gating and clustering over extended durations. Another benefit is elucidating cross-scale causal mechanisms, such as tracking the subcellular and cellular bioelectrical correlates of cancer metastasis. The article highlights the transformative potential of label-free optical technologies, which enable non-invasive, high-resolution monitoring of bioelectrical signals, offering the possibility of dense sampling across this spatiotemporal continuum. These advances now allow real-time visualization of ion channel gating, membrane potential fluctuations, emergent network dynamics, and *in vivo* bioelectrical activity. Furthermore, combining these label-free methods with fluorescence imaging, electrophysiology, and multimodal chemical and structural imaging provides a powerful pathway for advancing bioelectricity research and unlocking its translational potential in clinical applications.

Keywords: Integrative bioelectrical imaging – Bioelectricity – Ion channels – Membrane potential – Bioelectrical networks – Plasmonics – Label-free imaging – Quantum sensors – Electrochromic sensors.

1. Introduction

Bioelectricity has become increasingly central in addressing some of the most pressing healthcare challenges, including cancer diagnosis¹ and therapy², regenerative medicine³, antimicrobial resistance⁴, and the development of next generation bioelectronic interventions^{5,6}. For decades, bioelectrical measurements have primarily targeted excitable cell types — such as neurons, cardiomyocytes, and endocrine cells — yielding profound mechanistic insights into fundamental processes including information processing⁷, signal transmission⁸, and synchronization⁹. However, it is now evident that bioelectrical phenomena exert critical influences across a far broader spectrum of cell types¹⁰, emphasizing their universal role in cellular physiology and pathology¹¹.

Recent investigations employing voltage imaging have demonstrated that breast cancer cells exhibit spontaneous fluctuations in membrane potential, a phenomenon absent in non-malignant epithelial cells¹². These fluctuations emerge during the epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition, the cellular reprogramming process that underpins metastatic progression. These fluctuations exhibit temporal correlations among neighboring cells, indicative of electrical coordination within tumor microenvironments¹². A recent study of small-cell lung cancer¹³ showed that intrinsic electrical activity exerts a causal influence on both tumorigenic capacity and metastatic potential, as evidenced by optogenetic and pharmacological manipulations.

Beyond oncological contexts, endogenous electric states have been observed to influence processes such as wound healing¹⁴⁻¹⁶ and tissue regeneration, while dynamic fluctuations in membrane potential regulate metabolic states in bacterial biofilms¹⁷. Collectively, these findings position bioelectricity as a universal organizational principle in biology^{10,11,18} with capacity to regulate cell and tissue function. The phenomena described may represent only an initial glimpse of a broader integrative mechanism, with profound implications for both fundamental biology and translational medicine.

Driven by the vision to enable a comprehensive investigation into the multiscale and universal role of bioelectricity, this Perspective introduces a framework for examining bioelectric phenomena across broader spatial and temporal scales, exceeding the limitations imposed by current measurement technologies. Section 2 introduces this integrated spatial and temporal framework for bioelectrical imaging. Section 3 then explores the wide-ranging potential of recently developed label-free optical technologies, emphasizing their complementary relationship with existing tools. Finally, Section 4 provides an outlook, highlighting ongoing efforts to realize cross-scale bioelectrical screening.

2. Integrative cross-scale bioelectrical imaging framework

Bioelectricity functions across multiple interconnected scales, ranging from individual channel proteins to the entire organism³, as illustrated in Fig.1. To thoroughly capture the complex bioelectrical interactions, we propose a spatiotemporal framework (Fig.1), where examples of bioelectrical phenomena are represented along the diagonal axis (causal trajectory I) in accordance with their relevant physical scales and the durations of their dynamic processes. Ion channel and pump activity is one of the key mechanisms governing membrane potential and its dynamics, which in turn drives tissue-scale patterns evolving over hours to weeks³. Integrative mapping of this causal trajectory will illuminate the role of bioelectrical signals across spatial and temporal scales alongside processes such as proliferation¹⁹, adhesion²⁰, migration²¹ and higher-level outcomes including developmental patterning^{22,23}, tissue regeneration²⁰, cancer development^{1-3,10,12} and aging¹⁰. While the integration across scales links to the emergence of higher-order spatial (trajectory II) and temporal patterns (trajectory III), there is also a feedback mechanism whereby long-term changes may exert a top-down influence³ (trajectory IV). These workspace trajectories, illustrated in Fig. 1, suggest a series of hypotheses and measurement perspectives that demand new technical capabilities.

The essence of this concept lies in observing bioelectrical dynamics across multiple scales, moving beyond the study of isolated events, to examine causal influences, feedback loops, and their biological significance. For instance, studying morphogenesis²² and regeneration²³ — a gradual, tissue-scale process — while concurrently tracking membrane potentials has revealed the instructive role of the latter. Similarly, future hypotheses could be tested with experimental designs that follow specific temporal and spatial trajectories of a living system (Fig. 1). These trajectories could include investigating how the spatial and temporal patterns of ion channels activity contribute to higher-order cellular and network states²⁴ (trajectory II, Fig. 1), the effect of ion channel clustering²⁵ or explore their dynamic behavior over periods extending to several days (trajectory III, Fig. 1) and test the feedback influence of larger-scale higher-order processes (trajectory IV, Fig. 1).

While currently used tools are not optimized to span these scales and can only capture a limited window in the workspace depicted in Fig.1, newly developed label-free technology has the potential to support hypotheses that integrate across scales. For instance, no existing technique can simultaneously resolve single ion channel events and track network-level dynamics over the hours to days relevant to slow bioelectrically regulated processes. Patch-clamp electrophysiology provides exquisitely sensitive functional measurements of individual ion channels yet cannot capture how stochastic channel activity aggregates to generate emergent cellular or tissue-level signals. Whole-cell recordings resolve action potential waveforms but do not capture spatial and temporal dynamics of the collective. Microelectrode arrays permit chronic, multi-site measurements, but they only offer spatial resolution that is on the order of 10 μm ²⁶. Optical approaches, including voltage-sensitive dyes and genetically encoded indicators²⁷, can visualize membrane potential dynamics at the single-cell level,

but do not resolve ion channel dynamics. Furthermore, they require either pharmacological loading or transgenic expression and are limited by phototoxicity, confining continuous recordings to only several minutes.

Figure 1 **Cross-scale bioelectrical measurement workspace and bioelectric phenomena map** – A conceptual framework introduced to investigate bioelectrical phenomena across multiple spatial and temporal scales. Phenomena are illustrated through examples at the molecular, subcellular, cellular, network, and tissue levels, with each level contextualised by its characteristic size and the duration of its dynamic events. Four trajectories are presented as illustrative pathways in this framework, each defining both a perspective for measurement and a set of testable hypotheses. (I) – Cross-scale causation trajectory explores how the influence of bioelectricity propagates from ion channel events to influence cell, tissue, and organism-level states. (II) – Spatial integration trajectory focuses on the emergence of network and tissue-level signals from distributed patterns across elemental units. (III) – Emerging temporal patterns trajectory investigates whether extended monitoring of rapid molecular phenomena (e.g. ion channels gating) reveals distinct dynamic modes. (IV) – Cross-scale modulation investigates how higher-level processes provide feedback that influences lower cellular and molecular levels, while also considering the long-term effects of bottom-up modulation.

The next section highlights the breadth and versatility of label-free optical technologies, including electrochemically modulated interferometric scattering (EM-iSCAT)²⁸, plasmonic^{29–32} and electrochromic sensing^{33,34}, nitrogen-vacancy (NV) diamond voltammetry^{35–38}, and fiber-based plasmonic probes³⁹. Taken together, these optical microscopy techniques represent a powerful and highly integrable measurement toolkit, with continued research encouraged to showcase their potential in bridging temporal and spatial scales.

3. Label-free bioelectrical imaging: from single ion channels to cell networks

Exploring the spatial and temporal domains outlined in Section 2 requires innovative tools that complement existing bioelectrical and electrophysiological measurement techniques. In this section, we present a suite of technologies designed to span the wide range of spatial and temporal scales of

bioelectrical phenomena, as illustrated in Figure 1. These tools open up valuable opportunities for investigating the role of bioelectrical factors in slow biological processes, such as wound healing, morphogenesis, and tumorigenesis.

3.1. High-resolution functional imaging of ion channels

Label-free microscopy of ion dynamics has recently gained significant attention, offering substantial promise for high-resolution spatial and temporal imaging of ion channel activity²⁸. Sensing ion redistribution through the electrical double layer at electrode–electrolyte interfaces^{40–45} was pioneered by the Faez group at Utrecht University, utilising opto-iontronic microscopy to reveal charge dynamics and redox processes in nanostructures^{40,46}. This approach was initially demonstrated using a dark-field optical microscopy configuration⁴⁰ and subsequently advanced through interferometric scattering microscopy (iSCAT) to monitor lithium-ion dynamics during battery operation⁴². iSCAT leverages optical interference between scattering events and a partially reflecting substrate, enabling highly sensitive microscopy that has been successfully employed for single-protein detection among many applications in chemical and biological science.

Building on recent progress in imaging ion dynamics, Xu and colleagues at Nanjing University has introduced a pioneering electrochemically modulated iSCAT method²⁸ achieved by integrating electrochemical techniques with high-resolution microscopy. This breakthrough enables the first non-invasive functional imaging of ion channels (Fig.2). The underlying mechanism relies on detecting ion diffusion, which results from ion channel gating. This process generates subtle light scattering that interferes with the reference beam, which is partially reflected off the substrate. By employing electrochemical modulation as a carrier signal, the approach allows for the selective reconstruction of individual channel events, effectively separating them from background noise generated by random scattering.

Figure 2 **a**. Co-localization of individual NMDAR channels visualized using combined immunofluorescence and EM-iSCAT imaging. Scale bars: (1) 5 μm ; (2–4) 1 μm . **b**. Single-channel recordings (Ch 1–3) from NMDARs expressed in HEK-293 cells, with representative EM-iSCAT snapshots of selected channel-opening events (scale bars: 250 nm), alongside their corresponding positions (tracks denote the central coordinates from a Gaussian fit to the bright spots) and signal trajectories. **c**. Enlarged view of a segment from channel 3 (Ch 3, red dashed box), illustrating channel opening and closing times. Snapshot scale bars: 500 nm. Reproduced from Ref²⁸ with minor rearrangement of panels with permission from Springer Nature.

This platform has successfully resolved the activity of single ion channels with accurate spatial localization²⁸ (Fig.2) demonstrating rigorous characterization of the detected signal through a

combination of experimental and modeling approaches. This capability has been exemplified through experiments with HEK-293 cells expressing N-methyl-D-aspartate receptors (NMDARs) and further validated with correlative super-resolution profiling of ion channels (Fig.2-a). This approach shows promise to distinguish between various ion channel types, observe their opening and closing states, and identify patterns of clustering. In addition, the events of single channels and channel clusters in ligand-gated nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (nAChR) channels were tracked using cultured human neuroblastoma cells (SH-SY5Y), allowing for precise visualization and analysis of receptor organization.

The signal measured by EM-iSCAT may arise via two routes — (i) ion redistribution at the electrode double layer modulating local refractive index, and (ii) charge-induced shifts in the electron density of the electrode and thus its refractive index⁴⁷. Disentangling these factors is essential for quantitative measurement of ion channel current and, in principle, for identifying charge carriers⁴⁷. Our recent work has shown that ion redistribution within the double-layer capacitive region can induce variations in the refractive index of the Debye layer⁴⁷. The differing molar refractivities of individual cations and anions enable their respective contributions to the overall refractive index change to be resolved. In addition, ionic charge can influence the electron density within the electrode, producing a charge-dependent shift in refractive index. A key application of this study is the quantitative measurement of ion dynamics using iSCAT⁴⁷.

Label-free functional imaging of ion channels holds remarkable potential for advancing bioelectricity. Ion channels play a key role in cancer progression^{12,13}, serve as critical targets for cancer therapeutics², influence regeneration patterns²³, and display altered function with aging¹⁰, leading to cellular depolarization. Furthermore, label-free imaging offers the capability to monitor bioelectrical regulation over extended periods, opening unprecedented opportunities to explore the spatial and temporal dimensions of the workspace illustrated in Fig. 1.

3.2. Label-free sensing of membrane potential dynamics

Label-free sensing and imaging of membrane voltage dynamics has emerged as an area of considerable interest, attracting the attention of numerous research groups worldwide^{31,32,34,36,39,48,49} as covered in previous reviews^{49,50}. Research in this field has largely focused on the detection of action potentials in excitable cells, which presents a major engineering challenge due to the high-frequency response required (on the order of several kHz) and stringent signal-to-noise constraints. Nevertheless, various technologies have successfully demonstrated the non-fluorescent detection of action potentials.

Plasmonic sensors have exhibited the capability to map the propagation of neuronal action potentials³¹ (Fig.3) and to monitor cardiac action potentials (Fig.4c)⁴⁸ *in vitro*. Surface plasmon resonance (SPR) is achieved via optically induced collective oscillations of free electrons at the metal–dielectric, or metal–electrolyte, interface. While SPR has been predominantly utilized for probing molecular interactions at surfaces, it is inherently sensitive to voltage changes^{30,51}. Variations in surface charge density modulate the local refractive index of the metal, resulting in a measurable resonance shift. The voltage-dependent redistribution of ions within the double-layer regions serves as an additional factor, inducing local refractive index variations primarily governed by the molar refractivity of the ions.⁴⁷ This voltage sensitivity offers a powerful avenue for label-free, high-speed electrophysiological imaging. This technique holds considerable promise for monitoring action potentials and broader membrane voltage dynamics. However, achieving greater sensitivity, an expanded dynamic range, and precise quantification remains a substantial challenge. This is particularly crucial for measuring membrane potential in non-excitable cells, as these exhibit low, and slow variations, while the baseline membrane potential is of vital importance for characterizing the bioelectric state¹⁰.

Recent advances across materials science, artificial intelligence, and fabrication methods now offer powerful opportunities to overcome these limits. Of particular note, Yanik and colleagues at the University of California, Santa Cruz, have achieved superior detection of action potentials using plasmonic nanoantennae⁴⁸ (Fig4a-c). In their study, plasmonic nanorods coated with a thin layer of PEDOT:PSS served as the active material for sensing interfacial charge dynamics⁴⁸. This coating

enhanced sensor responsiveness to external stimuli while simultaneously offering increased electrical capacitance and biocompatibility, thereby improving cellular adhesion and sensitivity relative to bare gold surfaces⁴⁸.

The work of Cui lab has introduced sensitivity enhanced label-free electrochromic bioelectric sensing⁵². Thin polymeric films directly deposited on indium–tin–oxide substrates, functioning as electrochromic materials, have demonstrated impressive performance in detecting action potentials in both cardiomyocytes and hippocampal neurons³³ (Fig4d-f). Graphene-based sensors represent another class of electrochromic approaches, exhibiting the ability to detect extracellular action potentials. In these systems, the endogenous electric fields generated by action potentials induce shifts in the Fermi level of atomically thin graphene, thereby modulating its optical absorption³⁴.

While innovative materials present a promising avenue for enhancing sensitivity, artificial intelligence approaches have demonstrated significant potential in reconstructing signals with signal-to-noise ratios as low as -20 dB⁵³. Furthermore, deep learning methods can be trained to identify and suppress instrument-specific noise⁵⁴, thus revealing the underlying measured signals. Electrophysiological recordings have greatly benefited from the revolution in AI, impacting several areas such as signal enhancement and decomposition. These advances could also significantly benefit label-free techniques, an area that has not yet received much attention.

Figure 3 **a** Brightfield image of a rat hippocampal neuron with whole-cell patch clamp; **b** surface plasmon resonance microscopy image of the neuron–sensor interface; and simultaneous electrical recording (**c**) with corresponding plasmonic recording (**d**) of the neuronal action potential. Reproduced from Ref³¹ with permission from John Wiley & Sons.

The methods previously discussed show significant promise in monitoring membrane potential dynamics in non-excitable cells, where label-free techniques remain largely unexplored. A central challenge in plasmonic detection is its intrinsic non-specificity. Although it excels at sensitively detecting fluctuations in charge dynamics or transient changes in membrane potential, it cannot directly measure the baseline membrane potential. This baseline is a critical determinant of cell bioelectric state, serving as a key parameter in governing processes such as regeneration and morphogenesis. Overcoming this limitation will require further dedicated research.

Figure 4 **a.** depicts a dark-field spectroscopy setup designed to monitor light scattering from electroplasmic nanoantennae. **b.** presents a cardiomyocyte cultured on an array of plasmonic nanoantennae. **c.** illustrates an example of enhanced action potential detection using PEDOT:PSS-coated plasmonic nanoantennae. (**a–c**) Reproduced from ref⁴⁸ under a Creative Commons CC BY-NC. **d.** provides a micrograph of cultured hippocampal neurons. (**e**) and (**f**) demonstrate electrochromic, label-free detection of action potentials, with panel (**f**) showing the response under an activity-promoting stimulus. Reproduced from ref³³ under PNAS license.

3.3. Label-free optical imaging of bioelectrical networks

This Perspective presents an overview of advanced optical label-free techniques and their applications in the functional imaging of single ion channels, channel clustering, and the dynamics of membrane potential in excitable cells. While individual cell behavior is critical, biological systems operate collectively to coordinate essential physiological processes. Consequently, advancing the functional imaging of bioelectrical networks through label-free optical methods constitutes a pivotal step for the field.

Our group's recent work, summarised in Fig.5, has demonstrated the utility of surface plasmonic microscopy in monitoring electrical signalling within pancreatic β -cell networks exposed to elevated extracellular glucose³². These cells exhibit synchronous and correlated oscillations, which are effectively suppressed upon the application of calcium channel blockers. By integrating graph-theoretical approaches, functional connectivity and network dynamics are extracted using both amplitude- and phase-based measures. This analysis revealed dynamic temporal changes in connectivity, offering new insights into spatiotemporal patterns of the collectives. While label-free imaging has traditionally been applied to excitable cells, these approaches hold significant potential for elucidating the diverse spatial and temporal patterns of electrical signalling in broader cellular networks, including cancer cells, where coordinated behavior is also evident.

This study³² revealed an additional key observation worthy of discussion, particularly relevant to the cross-scale imaging concept introduced in Section 2. Signals were recorded within a $1 \mu\text{m}^2$ area, including both direct cell–sensor extracellular contacts and extracellular regions spatially distant from cells. This approach enabled assessment of correlations between signals averaged across entire cellular regions and cross-correlations among subcellular recordings³². Firstly, this serves as an example of cross-scale imaging, in which subcellular, cellular, and network levels are monitored

simultaneously. Secondly, while oscillations at the whole-cell level exhibited strong correlations, correlations between subcellular signals dropped, suggesting that coherent cellular behavior may emerge from locally disordered dynamics. This finding is highly valuable for exploring spatial and temporal coherence and understanding how the integration of stochastic local events influences order at higher scales. Such insights may guide efforts to drive cell networks towards order for regenerative medicine applications or towards disorder to suppress cancer progression or biofilm growth.

Figure 5 **a** – The top panel presents a surface plasmonic microscope image of pancreatic β -cells, highlighting regions of interest that indicate both direct sensor–cell contact and extracellular areas at distances from the cells. The bottom panel displays the Pearson correlations for regions of interest 1–5. **b** – Shown here is an example of time series data recorded under elevated glucose conditions from ROIs 1–5. The lower panel illustrates subcellular signals captured from over 7,000 channels, each with an area of $1 \mu\text{m}^2$. **c** – The top panel depicts a cross-correlation map of the subcellular-level signals, while the bottom panel shows the distribution of correlations across the various subcellular regions. Reproduced from ref³² under a Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 licence.

It is noteworthy to mention that our study³² revealed that electrical activity in extracellular regions, even when situated at a measurable distance from living cells, exhibits a pronounced correlation with signals detected directly at the cell–sensor interface. The introduction of this capability is substantially promising for bioelectricity research, where extracellular electrical phenomena, arising from the superposition of cell-generated signals, are pivotal to mechanisms including wound repair, and long-range cellular communication pathways.

3.4. Label-free *in vivo* bioelectrical imaging

Label-free optical measurements and tracking of bioelectrical signals *in vivo* was pioneered by Sang Beom Jun and colleagues³⁹. In their approach, surface plasmon resonance (SPR) sensing through an optical fiber enabled the monitoring of local field potentials in the rat somatosensory cortex under external electrical stimulation. Furthermore, the optical measurements were validated through direct comparison with conventional electrical recordings. These measurements present a considerable challenge. As shown in Fig. 6, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is evidently much lower compared to electrical recording. To reconstruct the signal, coherent averaging of evoked optically recorded signals was performed at 500-fold and 2000-fold. This approach is emphasized, with advocacy for further research to enhance SNR and accessibility to measurements sites, as it may offer a significant opportunity for advancing the field of bioelectrical sensing, with bioelectrical signals serving as reliable biophysical markers. Optical fiber-based sensing and imaging has advanced significantly, driven by innovations in nanofabrication and metamaterials⁵⁵, as well as the application of artificial intelligence⁵⁶

for endoscopic imaging through fibers⁵⁷. Plasmonic neural probes, employing gold-coated tapered fibers, have been developed to achieve enhanced neurotransmitter detection⁵⁸ alongside simultaneous optogenetic stimulation and electrical readout⁵⁹. These recent breakthroughs hold great promise for overcoming the challenges inherent in label-free *in vivo* sensing and imaging.

Nitrogen-vacancy (NV) defects in diamond have emerged as a quantum sensing method for tracking electrical signals using voltammetry³⁸ or magnetometry³⁵ configurations, with a great promise for *in vivo* bioelectrical imaging. NV diamond magnetometry has been introduced for tracking action potential propagation in intact marine worm *Myxicola infundibulum*³⁶ with magnetic field propagation not hindered by tissue electrical impedance. Furthermore, NV diamond quantum sensors were employed for non-invasive magnetocardiography (MCG) in rat⁶⁰ and human⁶¹. As a non-contact method, this approach offers a great potential for tracking cardiac electrical activity, with a great advantage in comparison to electrocardiography (ECG) where placing electrodes is challenging as in burn patients. With dynamic electrical signals observed in clinically relevant application such as cancer and wound healing, these contemporary non-contact and non-invasive approaches may represent a promising avenue.

Figure 6 **a**: Optical fiber–based surface plasmon resonance sensor designed for *in vivo* recording of electrical signals. **b**: Electrical recordings, with corresponding evoked optically recorded signals in **(c)**— single trace without averaging (top), 500-fold averaged signal (middle), and 2000-fold averaged signal (bottom). Adapted with permission from Ref³⁹ © Optica Publishing Group.

4. Outlook

Several areas are highlighted to advance cross-scale integrative imaging and its applications. First, label-free optical imaging approaches have been demonstrated across spatial scales ranging from single ion channels to entire networks; however, integrating these capabilities in a single optical platform remains an open challenge. Our recent work proposed a cross-scale framework linking subcellular signals to functional network connectivity³², yet further efforts are required to explicitly elucidate how ion channel events integrate in space and time to drive higher-order collective patterns. This is now a promising pursuit with the new advancement in single ion channel imaging²⁸. Although all the techniques discussed here are based on optical configurations that are integrable, such integration presents technical challenges. This includes the development of sensors and system configurations that enable cross-scale imaging and are immune to distorting crosstalk. Furthermore, innovative data

analytics for examining dense spatio-temporal data are crucial to support the extraction and presentation of relevant features and inform both fundamental discoveries and clinical applications.

Second, the development of label-free techniques is motivated by the need for robust alternatives to widely employed fluorescence-based and microelectrode methodologies. However, a synergistic approach, integrating label-free methods with conventional techniques, offers significant advantages. Label-free optical imaging can overcome several inherent limitations of existing tools; yet it is often challenged by non-specificity – a limitation that fluorescence imaging and electrical recordings are well suited to address. This principle of methodological complementarity can be further extended through correlative analytical frameworks including electron microscopy, chemical imaging, and transcriptomics, accelerating our capacity to elucidate the overarching biological roles of electrical phenomena. Measuring the resting membrane potential through label-free methods poses a considerable challenge, as these techniques are generally more sensitive to fluctuations in membrane potential than to absolute values. This represents an area where the integration of correlative fluorescent imaging, electrical measurements, and label-free imaging could offer a promising solution.

Third, cross-scale optical imaging is crucial for achieving a comprehensive understanding of bioelectrical regulation in biological systems. Employing label-free technology broadens the range of hypotheses that current methods cannot accommodate. For example, it allows investigation into how ion channel activity evolves over extended periods, how this activity influences higher-level processes, and how it is affected by complex bioelectrical and structural changes at different scales. This enhanced capability will significantly advance both our overall insight and our ability to precisely manipulate bioelectrical phenomena. Rigorous validation of this approach across a range of *in vitro* and *in vivo*⁶² models would enable meaningful cross-species comparisons. For instance, label-free methods described here are focused on 2D *in vitro* models; nonetheless, a gap persists between these 2D *in vitro* and *in vivo* systems. 3D cell cultures — such as spheroids, organoids, or pancreatic islets — are now widely employed to bridge this divide. Capturing electrical activity in these 3D constructs presents a challenge for label-free microscopy. For example, the measured signal represents the collective response of multiple cells, and such measurements require innovative approaches to interpret. However, merging label-free measurement with robust mathematical modeling, could provide a powerful framework for interpreting the electrical signatures of complex 3D cellular structures.

Fourth, recent advancements in bioelectricity have provided crucial insights into disease diagnosis and treatment, with significant implications for cancer, infections, tissue regeneration, and bioelectronics. For example, cancers exhibit unique electrical signatures, making label-free techniques ideal for minimally invasive measurements. These approaches can be enhanced by a suite of technologies, including optical microscopes for *ex vivo* diagnostics and *in vivo* optical fiber -based imaging. Similarly, cross-scale imaging offers a comprehensive platform that supports the development of therapies aimed at promoting tissue regeneration, suppressing cancer progression, and curing infections.

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